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1 **Rising perfluorocyclobutane (PFC-318, *c*-C₄F₈) emissions in**
2 **China from 2011 to 2020 inferred from atmospheric**
3 **observations**

4 **Yinuo Wang^{1,2}, Minde An^{3,4,5*}, Luke M. Western^{5,6}, Ronald G. Prinn³, Jianxin**
5 **Hu⁴, Xingchen Zhao⁴, Matthew Rigby^{3,5}, Jens Mühle⁷, Martin K. Vollmer⁸, Ray**
6 **F. Weiss⁷, Bo Yao^{1,9,10*}**

7 1 Department of Atmospheric and Oceanic Sciences & Institute of Atmospheric
8 Sciences, Fudan University, Shanghai 200438, China.

9 2. Shanghai Frontiers Science Center of Atmosphere-Ocean Interaction & Key
10 Laboratory of Polar Atmosphere-ocean-ice System for Weather and Climate, Ministry
11 of Education & Shanghai Key Laboratory of Ocean-land-atmosphere Boundary
12 Dynamics and Climate Change, Shanghai 200438, China.

13 3 Center for Global Change Science, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge,
14 Massachusetts 02139, United States.

15 4 College of Environmental Sciences and Engineering, Peking University, Beijing
16 100871, China.

17 5 School of Chemistry, University of Bristol, Bristol BS8 1TS, UK.

18 6 Global Monitoring Laboratory, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration,
19 Boulder, CO 80305, USA.

20 7 Scripps Institution of Oceanography, University of California San Diego, La Jolla,
21 CA 92083, USA.

22 8 Laboratory for Air Pollution and Environmental Technology, Empa, Swiss Federal
23 Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology, Dübendorf 8600, Switzerland.

24 9 Meteorological Observation Centre of China Meteorological Administration
25 (MOC/CMA), Beijing 100081, China.

26 10 National Observations and Research Station for Wetland Ecosystems of the
27 Yangtze Estuary, Fudan University, Shanghai 201112, China.

28

29 Corresponding authors:

30 Bo Yao: yaobo@fudan.edu.cn; Minde An: mindean@mit.edu

31

32 **Abstract**

33 Global atmospheric emissions of perfluorocyclobutane (*c*-C₄F₈, PFC-318), a potent greenhouse gas,
34 have increased rapidly in recent years. Combining atmospheric observations made at nine Chinese
35 sites with a Lagrangian dispersion model-based Bayesian inversion technique, we show that PFC-
36 318 emissions in China grew by approximately 70% from 2011 to 2020, rising from 0.65 (0.54–
37 0.72) Gg yr⁻¹ in 2011 to 1.12 (1.05–1.19) Gg yr⁻¹ in 2020. The PFC-318 emissions increase from
38 China played a substantial role in the overall increase in global emissions during the study period,
39 contributing 58% to the global total emissions increase. This growth predominantly originated in
40 eastern China. The regions with high emissions of PFC-318 in China overlap with areas densely
41 populated with polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) factories, implying that fluoropolymer factories are
42 important sources of PFC-318 emissions in China. Our investigation reveals an emission factor of
43 approximately 3.02 grams of by-product PFC-318 emissions per kilogram of
44 hydrochlorofluorocarbon-22 (HCFC-22) feedstock use in the production of tetrafluoroethylene
45 (TFE) (for PTFE production) and hexafluoropropylene (HFP), if we assume all HCFC-22 produced
46 for feedstock uses in China are pyrolyzed to produce PTFE and HFP. Further facility-level sampling
47 and analysis are needed for a more precise evaluation of emissions from these factories.

48 **Keywords:** perfluorocyclobutane, fluorinated greenhouse gases, emissions

49 **Synopsis:** Identifying China as one of the primary contributors to the global increase in PFC-318
50 emissions, resulting from PFC-318 being a byproduct of the pyrolysis of HCFC-22 to
51 tetrafluoroethylene (TFE) (for PTFE production) and hexafluoropropylene (HFP) in China.

52 **Introduction**

53 Perfluorocyclobutane (octafluorocyclobutane, *c*-C₄F₈, or PFC-318) is a potent greenhouse gas
54 (GHG). With an atmospheric lifetime of 3200 years, PFC-318 has a 100-year time horizon global
55 warming potential (GWP₁₀₀) of 10,200 (1). Previously, PFC-318 emissions were assumed to be
56 predominantly caused by its use for plasma etching in the semiconductor industry (2), but highly
57 efficient abatement due to modern emission controls can reduce emissions from the semiconductor
58 and microelectronics industry by up to 90%, making PFC-318 emissions from this industry likely
59 relatively low (3). Another potentially noteworthy source of PFC-318 is the production of

60 tetrafluoroethylene (TFE) and hexafluoropropylene (HFP) monomers (4-6). The primary method
61 for preparing TFE and HFP monomers is through the pyrolysis of hydrochlorofluorocarbon-22
62 (HCFC-22, CHClF_2). In this process, PFC-318 is formed as a byproduct of the dimerization of TFE.
63 By controlling the dimerization process of TFE, PFC-318 can be generated, and co-pyrolysis of
64 PFC-318 and TFE may also lead to the formation of HFP or PFC-318 (2,6-8,15). Mühle et al. (8)
65 showed that PFC-318 emissions were highly correlated with the use or production of HCFC-22
66 feedstock, observed both on a global scale and within developing (Article 5 of the Montreal Protocol,
67 A5) countries. Almost all global feedstock production of HCFC-22 is used to produce TFE and HFP,
68 which are subsequently used to produce polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) and other fluorinated
69 polymers and compounds (9), during which PFC-318 is formed as a byproduct and then likely
70 emitted into the atmosphere. Besides, PFC-318 is used as a minor component in food packaging
71 (10), refrigerants (11), and the electric insulation of gases (12).

72 Numerous studies have reported a global increase of PFC-318 atmospheric abundances since
73 the 1960s (13-17). At the beginning of the 1960s, the PFC-318 atmospheric mole fraction was close
74 to zero (<0.02 ppt), after which it rose sharply, which corresponded with the approximate timing of
75 its emergence as a byproduct of PTFE synthesis (8). The PFC-318 global mean mole fractions,
76 observed by Advanced Global Atmospheric Gases Experiment (AGAGE), have reached 1.82 ppt in
77 2020 (18).

78 Since the 1990s, many Annex I countries have adopted mitigation policies and measures and
79 are required to submit annual reports of their GHG emissions to UNFCCC (14). Global PFC-318
80 emissions declined from the mid-1990s to the early 21st century, likely reflecting reductions from
81 Annex I countries. However, global emissions have subsequently increased, reaching approximately
82 2.32 Gg yr^{-1} in 2020 (8). Prior research attributed this resurgence primarily to non-Annex I countries,
83 notably China (8). A previous top-down study allocated approximately 32% of global total PFC-
84 318 emissions to eastern China, where strong PFC-318 emissions were observed in heavily
85 industrialized provinces located south/southwest of Beijing and near the Yangtze River Delta
86 (15). Two bottom-up PFC-318 emission estimates have been compiled based on industry data
87 in China, one by the Emissions Database for Global Atmospheric Research (EDGAR) (19) and
88 the other by Guo et al. (20). However, large discrepancies exist between the two inventories.
89 For example, PFC-318 emissions from China in the EDGAR inventory were $<0.01 \text{ Gg yr}^{-1}$ over

1991 to 2021, which only included estimates for the electronics industry and no byproduct emissions from fluoropolymer synthesis (19). A top-down inverse modeling approach (based on atmospheric observations and statistical analysis) can be used to evaluate bottom-up inventories. However, current top-down estimates of PFC-318 emissions in China have previously only been available for the eastern part of the country, as they were derived from atmospheric measurements made at a site outside China (i.e., the Gosan measurement site in South Korea), with limited sensitivity to emissions beyond eastern China. Given the global growth of PFC-318 and China's important role in global PFC-318 emissions, new top-down estimates covering the whole of the country are timely.

Here, we estimated the annual PFC-318 emissions from China (defined as the Chinese mainland, excluding Hong Kong and Macao) in 2011–2020, using measurements from nine sites within the country and an inverse modelling approach. We investigated primary emission regions, further explored the relationship between HCFC-22 feedstock use and PFC-318 emissions and discussed China's contribution to global PFC-318 emissions.

104

105 **Materials and Methods**

106 **Sampling and analysis**

107 Atmospheric mole fraction measurements were conducted at nine stations located across China
108 from 2011 to 2020, operated by the China Meteorological Administration (CMA). Additional
109 information on the site locations and sampling frequency/period can be found in Table S1. Waliguan
110 (WLG) and Shangri-La (XGL) were high-altitude stations at elevations higher than 3500 m, from
111 which measurements represented background conditions. The other seven stations, Akedala (AKD),
112 Shangdianzi (SDZ), Lin'an (LAN), Xinfeng (XFG), Jinsha (JSA), Jiangjin (JGJ), and Longfengshan
113 (LFS), were located in rural areas near or downwind of the most important populated and industrial
114 regions in China. The sampling frequency was daily for JGJ and weekly for other sites except for
115 LAN. For LAN, air samples were collected weekly until December 2018, after which they were
116 collected daily. Stations were situated more than 20 km away from the nearest industrial areas,
117 except JGJ and LAN, which were located approximately 10 km from the closest industrial zones, to

118 avoid sampling air that is not well mixed originating from significantly polluted sources.

119 The sampling and analysis procedures were conducted as previously described (21-22). Briefly,
120 air samples were drawn from the top of each sampling site's tower using a membrane pump (KNF-
121 86; KNF Neuberger, Germany) through a sampling tube with a 10-mm outer diameter (Synflex-
122 1300; Eaton, Birmingham, AL, USA) and pressurized into a 3-L stainless steel canister (model X23-
123 2N; LabCommerce, Inc., San Jose, CA, USA). The sample are pressurized to approximately 20 psi
124 to mitigate potential contamination during subsequent transportation and other processes. Then, the
125 samples were transported to the Beijing laboratory of the CMA for subsequent analysis and
126 measurement. The dry air mole fractions of a wide range of trace gases, including PFC-318, were
127 subsequently quantified in each air sample. In addition to flask sampling at the above sites,
128 continuous in situ measurements were conducted every 2 h at SDZ before August 2012 and after
129 December 2015 as a part of the Advanced Global Atmospheric Gases Experiment network (23). The
130 sampling methodology for the in-situ measurements is the same as for the flask air sampling process
131 described above, with the exception that air was directly drawn into the analysis system from a
132 nearby tower using a pump.

133 To detect and correct the drift in detector sensitivity, each air or flask sample was bracketed by
134 the analyzes of 2L of a reference gas (termed working standard or quaternary standard) measurement.
135 The reference gas was calibrated against a tertiary standard every week for in-situ measurement or
136 every month for central lab analysis. Our measurements are reported as dry air mole fractions on
137 the SIO-14 calibration scale developed at the Scripps Institution of Oceanography. Samples
138 collected via flask sampling and in situ measurements were analyzed using a custom build pre-
139 concentration unit (Medusa) equipped with gas chromatographic system coupled with mass
140 spectrometric detection (6890/5975B GC/MS system; Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA)
141 (24-25). The precision of the PFC-318 measurements was estimated from the standard deviation of
142 replicate analyses of the standard gases at approximately 0.9% for in situ and 1% for flask air
143 measurements, respectively. For in situ measurements from SDZ, the mole fractions were averaged
144 every 24 hours to avoid the influence of correlated uncertainties (e.g., transport errors over the 3-
145 hour meteorology forecast window are likely to be highly correlated and diminish in time), and to
146 reduce computational cost. Each averaged SDZ in situ measurement is sufficiently spaced in time
147 to be considered independent. Consequently, a total of 5647 measurements were incorporated in the

148 inversion analysis following resampling.

149 The sensitivities of the measurements to emissions in China are shown in Figure S1, indicating
150 good coverage for emissions in most regions of China. The sensitivities of the measurements to
151 emissions do not exhibit significant inter-annual changes. The varying number of available stations
152 each year do not have a large influence on the derived emissions and their spatial distributions (see
153 Figure S2 and S3).

154 **Regional transport models and sensitivity**

155 The atmospheric observations described above were combined with the measurement
156 sensitivity to surface emissions and a Bayesian inference algorithm to solve for emissions. A detailed
157 description of the inversion framework can be found in previous studies (26-28). The sensitivity of
158 each measurement to emissions was calculated using 30-day backward-running air histories (or until
159 the particles left the computational domain, which is most of the cases) generated by the UK Met
160 Office's Numerical Atmospheric-dispersion Modeling Environment (NAME) (29), a Lagrangian
161 particle dispersion model designed to simulate the advection and turbulent diffusion of hypothetical
162 particles within the atmosphere. Most particles will have left the domain after the 30-day period.
163 The meteorological data employed in NAME were from the UK Met Office Unified Model (30).
164 The computational domain employed in this study ranged from 5°S to 74°N latitude and 55°E to
165 192°E longitude. The derived "footprints" (source-receptor relationships) were output at a
166 resolution of 0.352° longitude and 0.234° latitude. For each observation, particles were released
167 within a vertical range of ± 10 m from the sampling inlet and at a rate of 20,000 particles per hour
168 from the sampling time, thereby ensuring that particle trajectories adequately represented air parcel
169 transport within the domain. It was assumed that particles potentially interacted with surface
170 emissions when their vertical position ranged from 0 to 40 m above the ground (31). Sensitivity at
171 each grid was integrated over a 30-day period. The locations where particles left the boundaries
172 were also recorded to calculate the sensitivity of each measurement to boundary conditions, i.e., the
173 contribution to the modelled mole fraction not originating from emissions within the spatial extent
174 of the computational domain.

175 **Inversion algorithm and a priori information**

176 A hierarchical Bayesian inference approach was employed to estimate PFC-318 emissions in

177 China, as described by Ganesan et al., (32) and Say et al., (26). Grid cells in the computational
178 domain were aggregated into 150 basis functions after applying a quadtree algorithm to the mole
179 fraction contribution at each grid cell, calculated using the a priori emissions and the NAME
180 footprints (33). During the inversion, the scaling factors for a priori emission estimates in each basis
181 function, scaling factors for a priori boundary condition estimates (background values), and model
182 measurement uncertainty were solved for each year. The initial total a priori emission estimate in
183 China was assumed to be 0.42 Gg yr^{-1} , which was constant throughout the period and was the same
184 value as used in a previous top-down study (14). The total emissions were allocated in space using
185 the nightlight density data derived from the NOAA Defense Meteorological Program-Operational
186 Line-Scan System (https://ngdc.noaa.gov/eog/data/web_data/v4composites/). Density data for
187 nightlights, which indicate anthropogenic lighting visible from space during darkness, provide a
188 plausible indicator of PFC-318 emissions, which are likely to be associated with densely populated
189 regions and industrial areas. The a priori probability distribution of emission scaling factors was
190 assumed to have a log-normal distribution with shape parameters μ and σ having values of
191 0.2 and 0.8, respectively. This probability distribution, while not overly informative, effectively
192 bounded the scaling within a realistic interval (one order of magnitude) and with positive values. As
193 for the boundary conditions, the initial boundary condition estimates were calculated using the
194 NAME sensitivities to the four horizontal domain boundaries together with the background mole
195 fractions on the domain boundaries generated by a global 12-box model inversion using background
196 AGAGE data (8,34). The scaling factors for the a priori boundary conditions followed a log-normal
197 distribution with shape parameters μ and σ having values of 1.

198 The Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) method was used to solve the Bayesian inference.
199 The total number of iterations for MCMC sampling was set to 2.5×10^5 after a preliminary tuning
200 phase of 1.25×10^5 iterations. To mitigate potential biases in the early phase of the Markov chain,
201 the initial 5×10^4 samples from the chain were discarded. The mean values along with their
202 associated 68% uncertainty intervals (16%–84%, representing 1 standard deviation for Gaussian
203 uncertainties) from the Markov chain were reported as the PFC-318 emissions and their
204 uncertainties in China.

205

206 Results and discussion

207 PFC-318 Mole Fractions in China

208 Figure 1 presents the time series of PFC-318 atmospheric mole fractions spanning from 2011
209 to 2020 measured at the nine observation sites in China used to derive emissions in this study.
210 Enhanced mole fractions were persistently observed at all nine sites over 2011-2020, especially at
211 SDZ, LAN, and JGJ, located in eastern China or Sichuan Basin, which are greatly influenced by
212 industrialized areas they have. These findings suggest persistent PFC-318 emissions in China from
213 2011 to 2020. Slightly higher abundances concentrations were observed at the SDZ and LAN sites,
214 implying greater pollution levels in the vicinity of these two sites. Moreover, pollution at the SDZ
215 and LAN sites appears to have intensified over the years, indicating a potential increase in emissions.
216 The abundances at the XGL and WLG sites are lower than those at the other seven sites perhaps due
217 to their distance from pollution sources, making them more representative of background conditions,
218 with their observed values also aligning more closely with background levels (Mace Head in
219 Ireland).

220

221 **Figure 1.** PFC-318 mole fractions (in ppt) observed at the LAN, JGJ, LFS, SDZ, WLG, XGL, XFG, AKD and
222 JSA sites from 2011 to 2020. The background levels were obtained from Mace Head in Ireland (MHD) (MHD data
223 is from AGAGE, http://agage.eas.gatech.edu/data_achieve/agage).

224 PFC-318 emissions in China

225 We inferred a substantial increase in PFC-318 emissions in China during 2011–2020 (Figure
226 2), increasing from 0.65 (0.54–0.72) Gg yr⁻¹ in 2011 to 1.12 (1.05–1.19) Gg yr⁻¹ in 2020, with an

227 overall growth of 74% (57%-90%). The derived emissions were relatively insensitive to the a
228 priori emissions used in the inversion (Figure S4).

229

230 **Figure 2.** Emissions of PFC-318 estimated in this study and comparison with other reported estimates of PFC-318
231 in China using different methods (15,19-20) The EDGAR v7.0 (19) only reported nearly negligible PFC-318
232 emissions from the electronics industry in China. A new bottom-up analysis for 2011–2019 (blue line and shading)
233 from Guo et al. (20) considered PFC-318 emissions from three sectoral categories: C₃F₈ production, semiconductor
234 manufacture and HCFC-22 feedstock use. The result from Mühle et al. (15) is the regional PFC-318 emissions for
235 eastern China.

236

237 At present, substantial disparities exist between the two bottom-up inventory-based studies
238 (19-20). The emissions reported by Guo et al. (20) were substantially larger than those in EDGAR
239 v7.0; PFC-318 emissions in EDGAR v7.0 are negligible in China, at <0.01 Gg yr⁻¹ over 1991 to
240 2021, whereas estimates from Guo et al. (20) are on the order of 1 Gg yr⁻¹. In this study, our top-
241 down emission estimates agree reasonably well with the bottom-up estimates by Guo et al. (20)
242 within the calculated uncertainties. Notably, both emissions estimates in this study and from Guo
et al. demonstrate a prominent peak in emissions in 2013, followed by a subsequent decline, and a

243 renewed increase since 2015/2016. From Guo et al. (20), the interannual variations in PFC-318
244 bottom-up emissions were primarily attributed to the changes in PFC-318 emissions from the
245 HCFC-22 feedstock use source sector (pyrolyzing HCFC-22 to produce tetrafluoroethylene (TFE)
246 for PTFE production with PFC-318 as a by product). Our results were substantially larger than
247 those in the EDGAR inventory, suggesting missing sources or unrealistically low emission factors
248 (EF) in EDGAR v7.0. The EDGAR inventory provided estimates for emissions exclusively
249 originating from the electronics industry, potentially omitting a substantial contribution from
250 byproduct PFC-318 emissions from the production of TFE/HFP via HCFC-22 pyrolysis, as
251 highlighted by Mühle et al. (8). Therefore, if the EDGAR v7.0 emissions are correct for the
252 electronics industry, the top-down emission estimates suggest that HCFC-22 feedstock uses
253 contributed the vast majority of PFC-318 emissions in China and that the electronics industry
254 itself only explained a very small fraction of the national total. Our top-down results were slightly
255 higher than the top-down results reported by Mühle et al. (15), which only estimated emissions
256 from eastern China. When focusing on the same region of eastern China as Mühle et al. (15), the
257 two results have a similar general trend and are in the same magnitude, where the difference may
258 come from different inversion approaches and measurement data used (Figure S5). In this paper,
259 our definition of eastern China aligns with that of the Mühle et al. (15) study, encompassing
260 provinces such as Beijing, Tianjin, Hebei, Liaoning, Shandong, Shanxi, Jiangsu, Zhejiang, and
261 Shanghai. Our results indicate that emissions from eastern China contributed to approximately
262 66% of the national total.

263 **Spatial distribution of PFC-318 emissions**

264 Eastern China was the primary source region of PFC-318 emissions in China during the study
265 period (Figure 3). This region is characterized by a dense population and a high level of
266 industrialization. The region was also the largest contributor to the emission increase between the
267 periods 2011-2012 and 2017-2020 (Figure 3c). Notably, Shandong province and nearby regions
268 comprised a significant emission hotspot, with Shandong experiencing the highest increase in
269 emissions between the two periods among all the provinces, amounting to 0.21 (0.19–0.24) Gg
270 yr⁻¹ and accompanied by a growth rate of 200% (151%–234%). Interestingly, there were no
271 semiconductor factories in this region, but several TFE/PTFE/HFP factories in Shandong were

272 situated in areas with large PFC-318 emissions. This finding supports the suggestion that
273 byproduct emissions from the TFE/PTFE/HFP industry are the primary source of PFC-318
274 emissions in China. Jiangsu province, located in the Yangtze River Delta region, also exhibited
275 substantial PFC-318 emissions, although levels were lower than those in the Shandong region,
276 with an increase of 0.05 (0.03–0.07) Gg yr⁻¹ between the two periods, a growth of 91% (34%–
277 123%). Both semiconductor and TFE/PTFE/HFP factories in this region were located near PFC-
278 318 emission hotspots. In summary, our analysis of potential industrial PFC-318 point sources
279 revealed substantial alignment between PFC-318 emissions and factories that used HCFC-22
280 feedstock and moderate overlap with semiconductor factories. If effective emission reduction
281 measures or recovery methods are not put in place, the increase in Chinese demand for TFE might
282 lead to a continual rise in PFC-318 emissions. Ebnesajjad et al. (7), along with studies such as
283 Mierdel et al. (35), describe investigations regarding the adoption of advanced techniques in
284 electrochemical fluorination (ECF) and recycling procedures. These approaches not only promise
285 considerable decreases in byproduct generation but also potential energy savings and overall waste
286 reduction.

287

288 **Figure 3.** Spatial distribution of PFC-318 emissions in China. **a.** Mean PFC-318 emissions in 2011–
 289 2012. **b.** Mean PFC-318 emissions in 2017–2020. **c.** Difference between **a** and **b**. Black circles
 290 represent active measurement sites during the period, while green and gray triangles represent known
 291 TFE/PTFE/HFP and semiconductor factories, respectively.

292 **Relationship between PFC-318 emissions and HCFC-22 feedstock use in China**

293 Previous research has demonstrated that a substantial portion of global PFC-318 emissions
 294 originates from the pyrolysis of HCFC-22 feedstock to produce PTFE and HFP (8). A chemical
 295 relationship between PFC-318 emissions and HCFC-22 feedstock use (using HCFC-22 feedstock
 296 production as a proxy for feedstock use in that study) was demonstrated in Mühle et al. (8), with
 297 EFs of 3.1 ± 0.1 -grams and 3.3 ± 0.2 -grams PFC-318 emissions per kilogram of HCFC-22 feedstock
 298 for the global average and A5 countries, respectively. Although the production process of HCFC-

299 22 itself does not directly result in PFC-318 by-product emissions, nearly all global HCFC-22
300 production for feedstock uses is used to produce TFE and HFE (8), which makes it reasonable to
301 use HCFC-22 feedstock production as a proxy for HCFC-22 feedstock use in producing TFE and
302 HFE. Here, we investigate the relationship (emission factor) between HCFC-22 feedstock use and
303 PFC-318 emissions in China. Due to the lack of data on HCFC-22 feedstock use/consumption in
304 China, we assume that HCFC-22 feedstock use/consumption in China could be approximated by
305 HCFC-22 production for feedstock uses in China, considering that nearly all HCFC-22 feedstock
306 in China is utilized for the production of fluorinated polymers (36-37), with any remaining
307 uncertainty arising from imports and exports, as well as potential delays between production and
308 use/consumption. However, the imports and exports of HCFC-22 are minimal in China (38). The
309 HCFC-22 feedstock production data were obtained from Zhao et al. (39).

310 We found a similar interannual trend over 2011-2020 between PFC-318 emissions and
311 HCFC-22 feedstock use in China (39) (Figure 4a). This signifies the significant contribution of
312 byproduct PFC-318 emissions during HCFC-22 feedstock use to national PFC-318 emissions in
313 China. We calculated the EF between HCFC-22 feedstock use to produce TFE/HFP and PFC-318
314 emissions in China by linear regression. The linear fit between PFC-318 emissions and HCFC-22
315 feedstock use (using feedstock production as a proxy) in China (Figure 4b) revealed a strong
316 correlation ($R^2 = 0.8$, $p < 0.01$), with a slope (EF) of 3.02 ± 0.50 grams PFC-318 emissions per
317 kilogram of HCFC-22 feedstock (to produce TFE/HFP) and an intercept of $-0.24592 \text{ Gg yr}^{-1}$. The
318 EF in China, 3.02 ± 0.50 grams PFC-318 emissions per kilogram of HCFC-22 feedstock use, was
319 lower than the global average EF (3.1 ± 0.1 grams PFC-318 emissions per kilogram of HCFC-22
320 feedstock use) reported in Mühle et al. (8) and lower than the EFs of all A5 countries (3.3 ± 0.2
321 grams PFC-318 emissions per kilogram of HCFC-22 feedstock use) (8), but the differences are not
322 significant ($p > 0.05$).

323

324 **Figure 4. a.** HCFC-22 feedstock production (virtually the same as HCFC-22 feedstock use) (Gg
 325 yr⁻¹) and PFC-318 emissions (Gg yr⁻¹) in China during 2011–2020. **b.** The linear fit between HCFC-22
 326 feedstock production (virtually the same as HCFC-22 feedstock use) and PFC-318 emissions in China
 327 during 2011–2020.

328 **Contribution of emissions from China to global emissions**

329 The PFC-318 emissions in China derived in this study were compared to the total global
 330 emissions (Figure 5a), which were obtained from Laube and Tegtmeier (18). The results reveal
 331 that China’s PFC-318 emissions contributed to approximately 40% of the global total on average
 332 over 2011-2020. This proportion ranged from a minimum of 28% in 2012 to a maximum of 50%
 333 in 2013 (Figure 5a). The increase in PFC-318 emissions in China of 0.40 (0.35–0.48) Gg yr⁻¹ from
 334 2011-2012 to 2017-2020 accounted for approximately 58% of global emissions growth (0.7 (0.48-
 335 0.92) Gg yr⁻¹). These results highlight the significant role that China plays within the context of
 336 global PFC-318 emissions.

337 The HCFC-22 feedstock production in China was compared to the global total and that of A5
338 countries in 2011–2019 (Figure 5b). As shown in Figure 5b, the proportion of China’s HCFC-22
339 feedstock production to the global total fluctuated between 52% in 2018 and 63% in 2013. The
340 increase in China’s HCFC-22 feedstock production was 111 Gg yr^{-1} from 2011-2012 to 2017-
341 2019, accounting for approximately 50% of the global total increase in HCFC-22 feedstock
342 production (approximately 201 Gg yr^{-1}). Notably, the proportion of HCFC-22 feedstock
343 production in China to the global total was larger than the country’s proportion of PFC-318
344 emissions, supporting the finding that the EF in China could be smaller than the global average.

345 The disparity between China (39) and A5 countries total (40) in HCFC-22 feedstock
346 production increased significantly from 2018 to 2020, which may have indicated increased HCFC-
347 22 feedstock use to produce TFE/PTFE/HFP in other A5 countries (if we assume these HCFC-22
348 feedstock production is used to produce TFE/PTFE/HFP in the same country). This potential
349 HCFC-22 feedstock use in the production of TFE/PTFE/HFP in other A5 countries could
350 contribute substantially to global PFC-318 emissions. The potentially lower EF in China
351 compared to the average EF in all A5 countries from Mühle et al. (8) may imply higher EFs in A5
352 countries other than China. A comprehensive and prolonged atmospheric measurement campaign
353 for other A5 countries is needed to elucidate the country origins and the various country
354 contributions of global PFC-318 emissions.

355 As emphasized by Mühle et al. (15), major PTFE producers in China have confirmed PFC-
356 318 byproduct formation. Unless effective emission reduction measures or recovery methods are
357 implemented, PFC-318 emissions could continue to rise as Chinese demand for HCFC-
358 22/TFE/HFP/PTFE grows. These emissions could be reduced through process optimization,
359 abatement, or alternative manufacturing techniques such as electrochemical fluorination and waste
360 recycling (8).

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Figure 5. Comparison of PFC-318 emissions and HCFC-22 feedstock production (proxy for feedstock use) in

365

China with the global total during 2011–2020. **a.** Global and China’s PFC-318 emissions (Left Y axis), and China’s

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contributions (Right Y axis). **b.** Global and China’s HCFC-22 feedstock production (virtually the same as HCFC-

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22 feedstock use) (Left Y axis) and China’s contributions (Right Y axis). **c.** Changes in PFC-318 emissions and

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HCFC-22 feedstock production in China compared with the corresponding global changes during from 2011-2012

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to 2017-2020 (2017-2019 for production data due to the lack of production data in 2020). Global PFC-318

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emissions were taken from the Scientific Assessment of Ozone Depletion: 2022 (18); Global HCFC-22 feedstock

371

production data were taken from Jens Mühle. et al. (8); A5 countries HCFC-22 feedstock production data were

372

taken from United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) (40); Chinese HCFC-22 feedstock production data

373

were taken from the Zhao et al., (39). These HCFC-22 feedstock production data were used as proxies for HCFC-

374

22 feedstock use data in the analysis of this study.

375 **Data Availability**

376 Measurement data of PFC-318 from the Chinese network are provided in the Supporting
377 Information, Data file 1. Use of the Chinese measurement data in publications, reports, or
378 presentations requires the users to contact Bo Yao (yaobo@fudan.edu.cn).

379 **Supporting Information**

- 380 ● Data that support the findings of this study (Data S1).
- 381 ● The monitoring stations in China utilized for this study are detailed in Table S1. HCFC-318
382 feedstock production data for China, A5 countries, and the Global from 2011 to 2019 are
383 presented in Table S2; Figure S1 shows the sensitivities of the measurements to emissions in
384 China; Derived emissions from China using measurements from all sites or from only 5 sites
385 are shown in Figure S2, The spatial distribution of the inversion where only 5 sites were used
386 are shown in Figure S3; Figure S4 illustrates emissions inferred using various initial values for
387 a priori emissions; The PFC-318 emissions in eastern China from this study are compared with
388 those from a previous study in Figure S5; The posterior spatial distribution from the flat prior
389 can be found in Figure S6; Figure S7 shows the spatial distribution of PFC-318 emissions in
390 Eastern China.

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401 **Author Information**

402 **Corresponding Authors**

403 **Minde An** –Center for Global Change Science, Massachusetts Institute of
404 Technology, Cambridge, MA, USA; College of Environmental Sciences and
405 Engineering, Beijing, China; School of Chemistry, University of Bristol, Bristol, UK;
406 Email: mindean@mit.edu

407 **Bo Yao** – Department of Atmospheric and Oceanic Sciences & Institute of
408 Atmospheric Sciences, Fudan University, Shanghai, China; Meteorological Observation
409 Centre of China Meteorological Administration (MOC/CMA), Beijing, China; National
410 Observations and Research Station for Wetland Ecosystems of the Yangtze Estuary,
411 Fudan University, Shanghai, China; Email: yaobo@fudan.edu.cn.

412 **Authors**

413 **Yinuo Wang** - Department of Atmospheric and Oceanic Sciences & Institute of
414 Atmospheric Sciences, Fudan University, Shanghai, China; Shanghai Frontiers Science
415 Center of Atmosphere-Ocean Interaction & Key Laboratory of Polar Atmosphere-ocean-
416 ice System for Weather and Climate, Ministry of Education & Shanghai Key Laboratory of
417 Ocean-land-atmosphere Boundary Dynamics and Climate Change, Shanghai, China.

418 **Luke M. Western** - School of Chemistry, University of Bristol, Bristol, UK; Global
419 Monitoring Laboratory, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, Boulder,
420 CO, USA.

421 **Ronald G. Prinn** - Center for Global Change Science, Massachusetts Institute of
422 Technology, Cambridge, MA, USA.

423 **Jianxin Hu** - College of Environmental Sciences and Engineering, Peking University,
424 Beijing, China.

425 **Xingchen Zhao** - College of Environmental Sciences and Engineering, Peking
426 University, Beijing, China.

427 **Matthew Rigby**- Center for Global Change Science, Massachusetts Institute of
428 Technology, Cambridge, MA, USA; School of Chemistry, University of Bristol, Bristol,
429 UK.

430 **Jens Mühle** - Scripps Institution of Oceanography, University of California San Diego,
431 La Jolla, CA, USA.

432 **Martin K. Vollmer** - Laboratory for Air Pollution and Environmental Technology,
433 Empa, Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology, Dübendorf,
434 Switzerland.

435 **Ray F. Weiss** - Scripps Institution of Oceanography, University of California San
436 Diego, La Jolla, CA, USA.

437 **For Table of Contents Only**

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